

Quantum Brownian Motion of Gauge Fields Along the Ricci Flow and the Emergence of Yang-Mills Theory in the Presence of Einstein-Hilbert Action: Toward a Coherent Path-Integral Measure for the Standard Model and Gravity

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Abstract: We propose a novel theoretical framework bridging quantum field theory and general relativity, based on the Wiener stochastic process within the infinite-dimensional Hilbert space of quantum states. By constructing a rigorously defined path-integral measure for quantum fields, we explore the geometry of Ehresmann connections on a principal fiber bundle with intrinsic fractal structure inspired by Weierstrass-like functions. We show that background gravitational effects, conventionally described by the Einstein-Hilbert action, emerge naturally as an entropic consequence of the universe's geometric evolution under the Hamilton-Perelman Ricci flow. Through critical approximations, the stochastic dynamics reproduce the Yang-Mills action, including a dynamically generated gauge-fixing term that addresses the Gribov ambiguity via non-local mechanisms. Incorporating Grassmann-valued spinor fields and applying the Lichnerowicz formula for the perturbed Dirac operator, we demonstrate a structural correspondence between the requirements for a well-defined Wiener fractal measure and the fermionic and bosonic content of the Standard Model (including massive neutrinos) and $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetric Yang-Mills theory. These results suggest that the fundamental forces and gravity may emerge from a unified underlying fractal stochastic dynamics in a fluctuating spacetime manifold.

Keywords: Weierstrass functions, fractals, Wiener stochastic process, Wiener measure, Brownian motion, Laplace-Beltrami operator, principal bundle, Ehresmann connection, Bochner Laplacian, Weitzenböck formula, Lichnerowicz formula, $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetric Yang-Mills theory, Standard Model, Hamilton-Perelman Ricci flow, Einstein-Hilbert action.

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Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. Lebesgue Fractal Measure for Ehresmann Connections	4
3. Wiener Fractal Measure for Ehresmann Connections	9
4. Localizing the Wiener Fractal Measure via Spinors	13
5. Einstein-Hilbert Action for the Standard Model on S^3	18
6. Summary and Discussion	26
References	26

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent papers [37, 38], we have established a consistent definition for fractal (Weierstrass-like) function over a compact closed oriented Riemannian manifold M . The definition is simple, but in fact, generalizable to more complicated differential structures on such manifolds. To provide a self-contained article we aim to explain the definition here. But, before this, we need to fix some conventions. Let Δ be the Laplace-Beltrami operator on M , and $\{\lambda_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ be its spectrum including the degeneracies, while the monotonicity is assumed, i.e. $\lambda_i \rightarrow \infty$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, for each continuous $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we have the Fourier series

$$f \cong \sum_i f_i \phi_i, \quad \left(f_i = \int_M f \phi_i d\Omega \right) \quad (1.1)$$

where ϕ_i is the eigenfunction of Δ with eigenvalue λ_i , and $d\Omega$ is the Riemannian volume form on M , while the real numbers f_i s are the Laplace-Fourier coefficients. Actually, the congruence relation " \cong " denotes a correspondence between f and the Laplace-Fourier series $\sum_i f_i \phi_i$ which must be explained thoroughly. Of course, if $f \in C^1(M)$, then " \cong " becomes the equality. But, however, if $f \notin C^1(U)$ for each open $U \subset M$, then the congruence relation " \cong " could still be replaced by " $=$ " for some special cases, such as the well-known Weierstrass function on $M = S^1$. For general M , such functions are referred to as the Weierstrass-like or fractal functions. Therefore, the right hand side of (1.1), i.e. the Laplace-Fourier expansion of fractal functions, could be considered as the simplest way for understanding and studying fractal structures on M .

As mentioned above we have already shown that the Weierstrass-like functions fulfill the following definition.

Definition 1; *Let M be a compact closed oriented Riemannian manifold and $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous with Laplace-Fourier modes f_i , $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Also, suppose that the Laplace eigenvalues are denoted with $\{\lambda_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ which includes degeneracies. Then, we say f is a fractal function on M if and*

only if for each fixed values of $\sigma > 0$, $\mu \geq 0$, and $\ell_0 > 0$, there exists some i , so that:

$$\int_0^{|f_i|} e^{\sigma(\mu^2 + \lambda_i)x^2/2} dx > \ell_0. \quad (1.2)$$

The integral on the left hand side of (1.2) is known as the fractal norm of f_i and is denoted by $\ell_{\mu,\sigma}(f_i)$.

Accordinging the above definition we can introduce a well-defined norm on some interesting subset of continuous functions on M . Let \mathbf{C} be the set of all functions $f : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of which the congruence relation " \cong " of (1.1) becomes the equality (almost everywhere) on M . Then, we have the following definition for the *fractal metric*:

Definition 2; Assume that $f, g \in \mathbf{C}$ have Laplace-Fourier modes f_i and g_i , $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Also, suppose that the Laplace eigenvalues are denoted with $\{\lambda_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ which includes degeneracies. Then, for each fixed $\mu \geq 0$ and $\sigma > 0$, the fractal metric $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g)$ is defined as;

$$d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) = \text{Sup}_i \left| \int_{g_i}^{f_i} e^{\sigma(\mu^2 + \lambda_i)x^2/2} dx \right|, \quad (1.3)$$

where the supremum is taken over all Laplace-Fourier modes.

According to **Definition 1** and **Definition 2** it would be obvious that:

- i) $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) \geq 0$, for each $f, g \in \mathbf{C}$, while the equality arises if and only if $f = g$;
- ii) $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) = d_{\mu,\sigma}(g, f)$, for each $f, g \in \mathbf{C}$;
- iii) $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) \leq d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, h) + d_{\mu,\sigma}(h, g)$ for each $f, g, h \in \mathbf{C}$;
- iv) $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) < \infty$, for non-fractal functions $f, g \in \mathbf{C}$;
- v) $d_{\mu,\sigma}(f, g) = +\infty$, for functions $f, g \in \mathbf{C}$ with fractal f and non-fractal g .

Therefore $(\mathbf{C}, d_{\mu,\sigma})$ is a closed metric space which is symmetrically distributed around the zero function $f_0 : M \rightarrow \{0\}$, while the fractal functions setel at the infinite distance from f_0 . In fact, one may imagine \mathbf{C} as an infinite-dimensional disc which its boundary $\partial\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}_\infty$ is the space of Weierstrass-like or fractal functions on M . Moreover, \mathbf{C} is a vector space whose subspace \mathbf{C}_∞ is stable, i.e. if $f \in \mathbf{C}_\infty$ and $g \in \mathbf{C}$ is non-fractal, then $f + g \in \mathbf{C}_\infty$.

In [37, 38] we have argued that the entire path-integral formulation of scalar quantum field theory with and without the presence of the gravitational effects could be worked out by studying the Wiener stochastic process of elements of \mathbf{C} , wherein the traget space measure has been induced from the fractal metric $d_{\mu,\sigma}$ or equivalently from the fractal norm $\ell_{\mu,\sigma}$. In this paper we aim to show that the quantum Maxwell theory of electrodynamics and the Yang-Mills theories of weak and strong integractiions could be studied within the same framework. But, however, for the mentioned gauge theories one should generalize the fractality condition to differential forms on some closed compact oriented Riemannian manifold which is itself a principl bundle over M .

In fact, the study of such quantum gauge theories has been postponed to the last (the third) part of our perusal, because the formulations and geometric structures of Yang-Mills theories have a lot of common features with the gravitational aspects that we have considered in the previous (the second) part.

2. LEBESGUE FRACTAL MEASURE FOR EHRESMANN CONNECTIONS

Let (P, π, M, G) be a principal G -bundles over D -dimensional orientable Riemannian manifold (M, g) , wherein G is a compact Lie group with Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , and $\pi : P \rightarrow M$ is the projection map. We assume that P is closed, connected, and orientable. We also remember that any Ehresmann connection form ω on P is a \mathfrak{g} -valued one-form satisfying three conditions:

i) Horizontal Isomorphism: For each $p \in P$ the linear map $\pi_* : \ker \omega_p \rightarrow T_{\pi(p)}M$ is an isomorphism.

ii) Vertical Isomorphism: For each $p \in P$ the linear map $\omega : T_pP \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ is identity on vertical vectors.

iii) Equivariance Property: For any $h \in G$, we have: $R_h^*(\omega) = Ad_{h^{-1}}(\omega) = h^{-1}\omega h$, with $R_h : P \rightarrow P$ the right action of h , where with this ω is mostly called an *equivariant (de Rham) one-form on P* .

Indeed, any Ehresmann connection form ω is simply written as $\omega = \omega^a \otimes t_a$, where ω^a s are one-forms on P , and $\{t_a\}_{a=1}^{D_G}$, is a generator for G with $D_G = \dim G$. Hence, the fractality of ω is due to the fractality of ω^a s as one-forms on P .

Put a Riemannian metric on P , say \tilde{g} , and denote the corresponding Laplace-Beltrami operator with $\Delta^{\tilde{g}}$. Assume that \tilde{g} is right-invariant, i.e. for each $X, Y \in T_pP$ and any $h \in G$ we have: $\tilde{g}_p(X, Y) = \tilde{g}_{R_h(p)}(R_{h*}(X), R_{h*}(Y))$. The action of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}}$ on the equivariant de Rham form $\omega = \omega^a \otimes t_a$ is defined simply as: $\Delta^{\tilde{g}}\omega = (\Delta^{\tilde{g}}\omega^a) \otimes t_a$. Since $[R_h^*, \Delta^{\tilde{g}}] = [Ad_{h^{-1}}, \Delta^{\tilde{g}}] = 0$ for each $h \in G$, the Laplace-Beltrami operator $\Delta^{\tilde{g}}$ is diagonal on the space of equivariant de Rham forms on P . That is any equivariant de Rham form on P , e.g. an Ehresmann connection form, is uniquely decomposed to a (possibly infinite) summation of the Laplace-Beltrami equivariant eigenforms. We show the eigenvalues of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}}$ for equivariant one-forms with λ , whereas the corresponding degeneracy is labeled by i . In particular, according to the properties **(i)** or **(ii)** of Ehresmann connections ω is nowhere vanishing, hence admits no fractal mass as we showed in [37]. Therefore, upon [37, 38], the Ehresmann connection form ω is a Weierstrass-like (fractal) structure on P if for each $\ell_0 > 0$, and $\sigma > 0$, there exists some a and some Fourier-Laplace mode (λ, i) , so that;

$$\int_0^{|\omega_{\lambda,i}^a|} e^{\sigma\lambda x^2/2} dx > \ell_0. \quad (2.1)$$

wherein $\omega_{\lambda,i}^a$ is the Fourier-Laplace coefficient of ω^a for the i -th degenerate basis of the eigenvalue λ . In principle, we have already found a fractal norm for the Ehresmann connection forms on the corresponding Fourier-Laplace phase space, i.e.;

$$\ell_{\mu=0,\sigma}(\omega_{\lambda,i}^a) = \int_0^{|\omega_{\lambda,i}^a|} e^{\sigma\lambda x^2/2} dx. \quad (2.2)$$

Set $C_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{N} \in \mathbb{N}$, to be the space of Ehresmann connection forms ω with $\omega_{\lambda,i}^a = 0$ for $\lambda > \mathcal{N}$. Then, the fractal norm (2.2) induces a Lebesgue fractal measure on $C_{\mathcal{N}}$ as:

$$d\mu_{LF} = \prod dx_{\lambda,i}^a, \quad dx_{\lambda,i}^a = e^{\sigma\lambda(\omega_{\lambda,i}^a)^2/2} d\omega_{\lambda,i}^a, \quad (2.3)$$

for any group index a and all Fourier-Laplace modes (λ, i) included in $C_{\mathcal{N}}$. The Lebesgue fractal measure (2.3) helps us to work out the Wiener stochastic process for Ehresmann connections on (P, π, M, G) . It should be noted that, although the space of Ehresmann connection forms is merely an affine space rather than a vector space, $C_{\mathcal{N}}$ is a well-defined vector space, providing a natural framework for describing Brownian motion in the Wiener stochastic process.

To write down the promised formula we need to set some convention; If Q is a (pseudo-) Riemannian manifold with metric q , then by notations of $d\Omega_q$, $\langle | \rangle_q$, Δ^q , \star_q , and ∇^q we will mean respectively the Riemannian volume form, the induced inner product (on differential forms or tensor fields), the Laplacian operator, the Hodge star operator, and the Levi-Civita connection of q on the underlying manifold Q .

Now, upon the above convention one easily reads from (2.3) that;

$$d\mu_{LF} = \exp\left(\frac{\sigma}{2} \int_P \omega^a \wedge \star_{\tilde{g}} \Delta^{\tilde{g}} \omega^a\right) d\mu_L = \exp\left(\frac{\sigma}{2} \int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}}\right) d\mu_L, \quad (2.4)$$

wherein $d\mu_L = \prod d\omega_{\lambda, i}^a$ is the ordinary Lebesgue measure, while the summation on repeated group index a (even if both are either superscript or subscript) is assumed.

Actually, we assume that the metric of G is induced by orthogonality of t_a s in \mathfrak{g} as: $\langle t_a | t_b \rangle_{\mathfrak{g}} = \delta_{ab}$, which is defined within a left-invariant (ad-invariant) formula given by the Killing form on the semi-simple component: $\langle t_a | t_b \rangle_{\mathfrak{g}} \propto tr\{\text{ad}_{t_a} \text{ad}_{t_b}\}$. We may suppose that the induced left-invariant Riemannian metric generates a Haar measure on G , hence, the volume of G is the unity. We should also remind that for any local section $\varsigma : U \subset M \rightarrow P$, the pull-back of the Ehresmann connection form is a \mathfrak{g} -valued one-form on U , say $\varsigma^*(\omega) = A = A_i^a dx^i \otimes t_a$, that is the spatial part of the Yang-Mills (vector) potential. On the other hand, the curvature of ω is a \mathfrak{g} -valued two-form on P defined as $\Omega = \Omega^a \otimes t_a = d\omega + \omega \wedge \omega$, whose its pull-back along ς is referred to as the spatial part of the Yang-Mills strength field; $\varsigma^*(\Omega^a) = F^a = F_{ij}^a dx^i \wedge dx^j = \left(\partial_i A_j^a - \partial_j A_i^a + f_{bc}^a A_i^b A_j^c\right) dx^i \wedge dx^j$, wherein f_{bc}^a is the structure constant for the generators $\{t_a\}_{a=1}^{DG}$, i.e., $[t_a, t_b] = f_{ab}^c t_c$.

Although \tilde{g} is arbitrary, for each given Ehresmann connection form ω there exists an induced metric on P which has a significant role in studying Yang-Mills theories. To see this with more details fix the Ehresmann connection ω and assume that $H_p = \ker \omega_p \subset T_p P$ be the horizontal space at $p \in P$. The induced metric \tilde{g}^ω is defined as:

$$\tilde{g}_p^\omega(X, Y) = \delta_{ab} X_V^a Y_V^b + g_{\pi(p)}(\pi_*(X_H), \pi_*(Y_H)), \quad (2.5)$$

for $X, Y \in T_p P$ and $X = X_V + X_H$ the corresponding vertical/horizontal decomposition of X due to ω . It is obvious that \tilde{g}^ω is a right-invariant metric. The following theorem has a crucial role in our study.

Theorem 1; *Suppose that (P, π, M, G) is a principal G -bundle on closed oriented Riemannian manifold (M, g) , where G is a compact Lie group. Set a connection on P with Ehresmann connection form ω and let \tilde{g}^ω be its induced Riemannian metric on P due to (2.5) Therefore, we have;*

$$\int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \int_P \langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} - c_0 = \int_M \frac{1}{4} \langle F^a | F^a \rangle_g d\Omega_g - c_0, \quad (2.6)$$

wherein $c_0 \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a constant. The exponent term of the Lebesgue fractal measure for \tilde{g}^ω is effectively the spatial term of the gauge invariant Yang-Mills action.

Proof; Actually, the main part of the theorem is locally, hence we should employ local differential structures for proving the assertion. Let $U \subset M$ be a trivialization chart as $\pi^{-1}(U) \cong U \times G$, together with local coordinate functions $\{x^i\}_{i=1}^D$ on U , and $\{y^a\}_{a=1}^{D_G}$ on some open set $V \subset G$ including the identity element $e \in G$ with $\partial_a|_e = \frac{\partial}{\partial y^a}|_e = t_a$. Hence, $(x^\alpha) = (x^i, y^a)$ is a local coordinate system on P , wherein the Greek letters $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots$ are generally used for addressing both the spatial coordinate indices i, j, k, \dots and those of the standard fiber labeled with $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \dots$. Since G is flat, y^a s could be chosen so that the right-invariant metric of G , say g^G , which is, in fact, the restriction of \tilde{g} to the fibers of (P, π, M, G) , turns into the Euclidean metric; i.e. $g^G = g_{ab}^G dy^a \otimes dy^b = \delta_{ab} dy^a \otimes dy^b$.

Set $\omega^a = \omega_\alpha^a dx^\alpha = \gamma_\alpha^a (dy^a + \alpha_i^a dx^i)$, where $\gamma : TG \rightarrow T_e G = \mathfrak{g}$ is the trivialization map defined as $\gamma := l_{h^{-1}*}$ on $T_h G$, for $l_h : G \rightarrow G$ the left-action by $h \in G$. Indeed, $\gamma(h) : T_h G \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ is a unitary matrix for each h . We obtain:

$$\tilde{g}_{ab}^\omega = \delta_{ab}, \quad \tilde{g}_{ia}^\omega = \tilde{g}_{ai}^\omega = \delta_{ab} \alpha_i^b, \quad \tilde{g}_{ij}^\omega = g_{ij} + \alpha_i^a \alpha_j^b \delta_{ab}, \quad (2.7)$$

and;

$$\tilde{g}_\omega^{ab} = \delta^{ab} + \alpha_i^a \alpha_j^b g^{ij}, \quad \tilde{g}_\omega^{ia} = \tilde{g}_\omega^{ai} = -g^{ij} \alpha_j^a, \quad \tilde{g}_\omega^{ij} = g^{ij}, \quad (2.8)$$

wherein $\tilde{g}_\omega^{\alpha\beta}$ is the inverse matrix of $\tilde{g}_\omega^{\alpha\beta}$. Actually, if we set;

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{I}_{D_G \times D_G} & -A \\ 0 & \mathbb{I}_{D \times D} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.9)$$

for $A_{ai} = \delta_{ab} \alpha_i^b$, one obtains: $J^T \tilde{g}^\omega J = g^G \oplus g$. Thus, we compute: $\det \tilde{g}^\omega = \det g$. Therefore, we readily have: $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = d\Omega_g \wedge d\Omega_G$, for $d\Omega_G$ the Haar measure of G . This proves the second equality of (2.6), since both $\langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ and $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ are gauge invariant, hence, $\langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ is constant on each fiber of P . Consequently, it is enough to prove the first equality in (2.6).

Note that according to property $R_h^*(\omega) = Ad_{h^{-1}}(\omega)$ we see:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\partial_a} \omega^a &= (d\mathbf{i}_a + \mathbf{i}_a d) \omega^a = d\gamma_a^a + \mathbf{i}_a \left(\partial_\beta \omega_\alpha^a dx^\beta \wedge dx^\alpha \right) = \partial_a \omega_\alpha^a dx^\alpha, \\ L_{\partial_a} \omega^a &= \left. \frac{d}{ds} \right|_{s=0} \left(R_{h(s)}^*(\omega) \right)^a = \left. \frac{d}{ds} \right|_{s=0} \left(Ad_{h(s)^{-1}}(\omega) \right)^a = f_{bc}^a \omega_\alpha^b \gamma_a^c dx^\alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

for \mathbf{i}_a and L_{∂_a} respectively the interior product operator of and the Lie derivative with respect to $\partial_a = \partial/\partial x^a$. In addition, $h(s)$ is a smooth curve in G which is chosen so that $R_{h(s)}(p)$ is the integral curve of ∂_a in V initiating from $p \in V$ at $s = 0$. Therefore, we read:

$$\frac{\partial \omega_\alpha^a}{\partial y^a} = f_{bc}^a \omega_\alpha^b \gamma_a^c, \quad (2.11)$$

which leads to the following identities:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma_a^a}{\partial y^b} = f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^b \gamma_b^c, \quad \frac{\partial \alpha_i^a}{\partial y^b} = \frac{\partial \tilde{g}_{\alpha\beta}^\omega}{\partial y^b} = \frac{\partial \tilde{g}_\omega^{\alpha\beta}}{\partial y^b} = 0. \quad (2.12)$$

Moreover, based on (2.8) it can be easily seen that:

$$\langle df|\omega^a\rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \partial_a f \gamma_b^a \delta^{ab}, \quad (2.13)$$

for any $f \in C^\infty(P)$. Thus, according to (2.12) we read

$$\int_P \langle df|\omega^a\rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \int_P \partial_a f \gamma_b^a \delta^{ab} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = - \int_P f \partial_a \gamma_b^a \delta^{ab} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = -f_{bc}^a \delta^{bc} \int_P f d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 0, \quad (2.14)$$

since f_{bc}^a is antisymmetric in b and c . Hence;

$$d^\dagger \omega^a = -\text{div}(\omega^a) = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

Thus;

$$\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a = d^\dagger d\omega^a \quad (2.16)$$

or equivalently:

$$\int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \int_P \langle d\omega^a | d\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega}. \quad (2.17)$$

On the other hand, upon (2.8) one obtains $\langle dy^a + \alpha_i^a dx^i | dy^b + \alpha_j^b dx^j \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \delta^{ab}$, hence, we read;

$$\langle \omega^a | \omega^b \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \delta^{ab}. \quad (2.18)$$

Therefore:

$$\langle f_{bc}^a \omega^b \wedge \omega^c | f_{de}^a \omega^d \wedge \omega^e \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 2f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \delta^{ce}. \quad (2.19)$$

In addition, the Christoffel symbols $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha$ of the Levi-Civita connection of the induced metric \tilde{g}^ω are:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Gamma}_{bc}^a &= \tilde{\Gamma}_{ab}^c = 0, \\ \tilde{\Gamma}_{bi}^a &= \tilde{\Gamma}_{ib}^a = \frac{1}{2} g^{jk} \delta_{bc} \alpha_k^a (\partial_j \alpha_i^c - \partial_i \alpha_j^c), \\ \tilde{\Gamma}_{ja}^i &= \tilde{\Gamma}_{aj}^i = \frac{1}{2} g^{ik} \delta_{ab} (\partial_j \alpha_k^b - \partial_k \alpha_j^b), \\ \tilde{\Gamma}_{jk}^i &= \Gamma_{jk}^i + \frac{1}{2} g^{il} \delta_{ab} \left\{ \alpha_j^a (\partial_k \alpha_l^b - \partial_l \alpha_k^b) + \alpha_k^a (\partial_j \alpha_l^b - \partial_l \alpha_j^b) \right\}, \\ \tilde{\Gamma}_{ij}^a &= -\alpha_k^a \Gamma_{ij}^k + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_i \alpha_j^a + \partial_j \alpha_i^a) + \frac{1}{2} g^{kl} \delta_{bc} \alpha_k^a \left\{ \alpha_i^b (\partial_l \alpha_j^c - \partial_j \alpha_l^c) + \alpha_j^b (\partial_l \alpha_i^c - \partial_i \alpha_l^c) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

wherein Γ_{jk}^i is the Christoffel symbol for g , the Riemannian metric of M . Employing the above equations we see:

$$\nabla_a^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a = -f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^b \omega^c, \quad \nabla_i^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a = \frac{1}{2} \gamma_a^a (\partial_i \alpha_j^a + \partial_j \alpha_i^a) dx^j. \quad (2.21)$$

We also have:

$$\langle \omega^a | \nabla_i^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^b \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 0. \quad (2.22)$$

Moreover, we need another identity to prove the theorem:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_P \langle d\omega^a | f_{bc}^a \omega^b \wedge \omega^c \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} &= f_{bc}^a \int_P \langle \omega^a | \tilde{g}_\omega^{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{i}_\alpha \nabla_\beta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} (\omega^b \wedge \omega^c) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} \\ &= 2f_{bc}^a \int_P \tilde{g}_\omega^{\alpha\beta} (\mathbf{i}_\alpha \omega^b) \langle \omega^a | \nabla_\beta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^c \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 2f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \delta^{ce} \int_P d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

where \mathbf{i}_β is the interior product operator for tangent vector $\partial_\beta = \partial/\partial x^\beta$, while the second equality comes from (2.15) and the last one is an immediate result of (2.21) and (2.22). Consequently, from (2.17), (2.19), and (2.23) we readily obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_P \langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} &= \int_P \langle d\omega^a + \frac{1}{2} f_{bc}^a \omega^b \wedge \omega^c | d\omega^a + \frac{1}{2} f_{de}^a \omega^d \wedge \omega^e \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} \\ &= \int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} + \frac{1}{2} f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \delta^{ce} \int_P d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} + f_{bc}^a \int_P \langle d\omega^a | \omega^b \wedge \omega^c \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} \\ &= \int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} + \frac{5}{2} f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \delta^{ce} \int_P d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = \int_P \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} + c_0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

for

$$c_0 = \frac{5}{2} f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \delta^{ce} \int_P d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega}. \quad (2.25)$$

This finishes the theorem. **Q.E.D.**

Upon the proof of the above theorem one concludes that for any arbitrary Ehresmann connection ω the induced metric \tilde{g}^ω leads to a trivial separation of the Riemannian volume form $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = d\Omega_g \wedge d\Omega_G$. Also, we assumed that the original metric of P , \tilde{g} , is itself an induced metric for some fixed connection structure on P with the Ehresmann connection ω_0 ; i.e. $\tilde{g} = \tilde{g}^{\omega_0}$. Hence, due to **Theorem 1** we read: $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}} = d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^{\omega_0}} = d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = d\Omega_g \wedge d\Omega_G$. Therefore, one could rewrite the Lebesgue fractal measure as:

$$d\mu_{LF} = \exp\left(\frac{\sigma}{4} \int_M \sqrt{\det g} F_{ij}^a F^{aij} d^D x\right) \exp\left(\frac{\sigma}{2} \int_P GF(\omega^a) d\Omega_{\tilde{g}}\right) d\mu'_L, \quad (2.26)$$

for $d\mu'_L = e^{-c_0} d\mu_L$, and

$$GF(\omega) = \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}} - \langle \omega^a | \Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega}. \quad (2.27)$$

In fact, the first exponent of (2.26) is the spatial component of the Yang-Mills action, and the second one (2.27) is indeed the gauge fixing term. Actually, this identity shows that the gauge fixing term is basically a non-local term, hence could not be written as a local functional of the Yang-Mills potential A_i^a in the Lagrangian density. Thus, the Lebesgue fractal measure (2.26) addresses the problem of Gribov ambiguity [20] to the non-locality of the original gauge fixing mechanism of the Yang-Mills action.¹

On the other hand, the ordinary gauge fixing term of Yang-Mills action is in fact accompanied with some ghost/anti-ghost field terms via the Faddeev-Popov path-integral formulation. However, as we see the Lebesgue fractal measure (2.26) only consists of real valued fields (differential forms)

¹ See [34] for geometric description of the problem.

with no contributions of Grassmannian-valued functions.² Therefore, it seems that emerging of such bizarre entities within a formulation of a fundamental force on nature is, in particular, an inevitable effect of non-local structures included in the formalism. More precisely, to convert a non-local feature of the Wiener fractal measure to a local term included in the Lagrangian density one has to employ some appropriate anti-commuting superfields due. In the following, we will face this phenomenon once again to obtain a local formula for the Yang-Mills Lagrangian density.

3. WIENER FRACTAL MEASURE FOR EHRESMANN CONNECTIONS

We remember that the stochastic process for Brownian motion in D -dimensional Cartesian space \mathbb{R}^D is well described by the Wiener probability measure

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_N)^{D/2}} e^{-|x(t_N)-x(t_{N-1})|^2/2\tau_N} d^D x(t_N) \times \dots \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_1)^{D/2}} e^{-|x(t_1)-x(t_0)|^2/2\tau_1} d^D x(t_1), \quad (3.1)$$

for the time slicing $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{N-1} < t_N$, the slice width $\tau_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$, $1 \leq i \leq N$, and the Euclidean norm $|x|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^D (x^i)^2$, for each $x = (x^1, \dots, x^D) \in \mathbb{R}^D$. As we stated in [37], for known *in* and *out* positions, i.e. for fixed $x(t_0)$ and $x(t_{N+1})$, the symmetric form of (5.31) would be

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) = (4\pi T)^{D/2} \exp(|x(T) - x(-T)|^2/4\pi T) \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_{N+1})^{D/2}} e^{-|x(T)-x(t_N)|^2/2\tau_{N+1}} d^D x(t_N) \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_N)^{D/2}} e^{-|x(t_N)-x(t_{N-1})|^2/2\tau_N} \times \dots \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_2)^{D/2}} e^{-|x(t_2)-x(t_1)|^2/2\tau_2} d^D x(t_1) \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_1)^{D/2}} e^{-|x(t_1)-x(-T)|^2/2\tau_N}, \quad (3.2)$$

for $t_0 = -T$ and $t_{N+1} = T$. Hence, the Brownian motion of fractal Ehresmann connections on P with identical *in* and *out* states, the so called *periodicity condition in the time dimension*, and restricting the Fourier-Laplace expansion into C_N , is described in terms of the Lebesgue fractal measure (2.26) and the symmetric Wiener measure (5.32) as;

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) = \mathfrak{C} \prod_{i=1}^N \Xi_i, \quad (3.3)$$

for

$$\mathfrak{C} = (2T/\tau_{N+1})^{D_N/2} \exp \left\{ - \left| \sum_{a,\lambda,i} \int_{\omega_{\lambda^a,i}(t_N)}^{\omega_{\lambda^a,i}(T)} e^{\sigma\lambda x^2/2} dx \right|^2 / 2\tau_{N+1} \right\}, \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$\Xi_i = \exp \left\{ - \sum_{a,\lambda,j} \left| \int_{\omega_{\lambda^a,j}(t_{i-1})}^{\omega_{\lambda^a,j}(t_i)} e^{\sigma\lambda x^2/2} dx \right|^2 / 2\tau_i \right\} \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\sigma}{8} \int_M \langle F^a(t_i) | F^a(t_i) \rangle_g d\Omega_g \right\} \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\sigma}{2} \int_P GF(\omega)(t_i) d\Omega_{\tilde{g}} \right\} d\bar{\mu}_L(\tau_i), \quad (3.5)$$

² See [35, 36] for more details about the background geometry of gauge fixing mechanism via the Faddeev-Popov quantization approach.

with $D_{\mathcal{N}} = \dim C_{\mathcal{N}}$, and $d\bar{\mu}_L(\tau_i) = (2\pi\tau_i)^{-D_{\mathcal{N}}/2} d\mu'_L(t_i)$. In fact, the Wiener fractal measure (5.33) is known as the most general formulation for studying the Brownian motion of fractal geometry of Ehresmann connection forms on P . However, including non-local terms, Ξ_i s could not be rewritten as a local Lagrangian density, unless one employs some appropriate approximation and mathematical tricks. At the first step let us use the following approximation:

Approximation I: *We may consider the following replacement in the first exponent of Ξ_i ;*

$$\frac{1}{\tau_i} \int_{\omega_{\lambda,j}^a(t_{i-1})}^{\omega_{\lambda,j}^a(t_i)} e^{\sigma\lambda x^2/2} dx \approx e^{\sigma\lambda(\omega_{\lambda,j}^a)^2/2} \partial_t \omega_{\lambda,j}^a(t_i) \quad \mapsto \quad \partial_t \omega_{\lambda,j}^a(t_i) \quad (3.6)$$

whenever $N \rightarrow \infty$ or equivalently $\tau_i \rightarrow 0$.

Let $\tau_i = \theta = 2T/N$ for each $1 \leq i \leq N$ and assume $N \rightarrow \infty$. Then, upon the approximation **I** we read from (3.6);

$$\Xi_i = \exp \left(-\frac{\theta\kappa}{2} \int_P \left\{ \langle \partial_0 \omega^a(t_i) | \partial_0 \omega^a(t_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} - \langle \Omega^a(t_i) | \Omega^a(t_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} \right\} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} \right) \mathfrak{G}_i d\bar{\mu}_L(t_i), \quad (3.7)$$

for $\kappa = \sigma/\theta$, $\partial_0 = \partial/\partial x^0$ with $x^0 = \sqrt{\kappa}t$, and $d\bar{\mu}_L(t_i) = (2\pi\theta)^{-D_{\mathcal{N}}/2} d\mu'_L(t_i)$, while

$$\mathfrak{G}_i = \exp \left\{ \frac{\sigma}{2} \int_P GF(\omega)(t_i) d\Omega_{\tilde{g}} \right\}. \quad (3.8)$$

is the gauge fixing term. Therefore, as $\theta \rightarrow 0$, by replacing $\theta \rightarrow dt$ one obtains;

$$\prod_{i=1}^N \Xi_i = \exp \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \left\{ \langle d_0 \omega^a(t) | d_0 \omega^a(t) \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} + \langle \Omega^a(t) | \Omega^a(t) \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} \right\} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} \right) \mathfrak{G} \mathfrak{D}\omega, \quad (3.9)$$

for

$$\mathfrak{G} = \prod_{i=1}^N \mathfrak{G}_i = \exp \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} GF(\omega)(t) d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

and $\mathfrak{D}\omega = \prod_{i=1}^N d\bar{\mu}_L(t_i)$, while $\mathcal{P} = [-T, T] \times P$ is the total manifold equipped with Lorentzian metric $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t) = dx^0 \otimes dx^0 - \tilde{g}^\omega(t)$ and the corresponding Riemannian volume form $d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} = dx^0 \wedge d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}$. Also, d_0 is, in fact, the exterior differential operator on the interval $[-T, T]$. Actually, $(\mathcal{P}, id_t \times \pi, \mathcal{M}, G)$ is a principal G -bundle over the Lorentzian manifold $(\mathcal{M}, \mathbf{g})$, wherein $\mathcal{M} = [-T, T] \times M$ is the space-time continuum,³ $id_t : [-T, T] \rightarrow [-T, T]$ is the identity map, and $\mathbf{g} = dx^0 \otimes dx^0 - g$ is the emergent Lorentzian metric on \mathcal{M} . However, we should emphasize that the exponent term of (3.7) could not be written as an integration of a local term on the space-time manifold \mathcal{M} . To overcome this problem one should add (and subtract) some appropriate terms to the exponent so that the resultant integrand becomes a gauge invariant functional on \mathcal{P} .

In order to convert the exponent term of (3.9) to a local functional on \mathcal{M} we should employ **Theorem 1**. Initially we define a new Ehresmann connection form with; $\tilde{\omega} = \omega + \beta := \tilde{\omega}^a \otimes t_a$, where

³ As mentioned in [37, 38] we deliberately use the terminology of *space-time*, instead of *spacetime*, to insist on the different substances of space and time dimensions in our stochastic based formalism.

$\beta = \beta^a \otimes t_a = \omega_0^a dx^0 \otimes t_a$, for some collection of one-forms $\{\beta^a = \omega_0^a dx^0\}_{a=1}^{D_G}$. As we explained in the proof of **Theorem 1**, on a local trivialization chart of $\mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ we have: $\omega_0^a = \gamma_a^a \alpha_0^a$, where; $\partial_b \alpha_0^a = 0$, for each $1 \leq b \leq D_G$. If \mathbf{d} is the exterior differential operator on \mathcal{P} , and $\tilde{\Omega}^a \otimes t_a = \mathbf{d}\tilde{\omega} + \tilde{\omega} \wedge \tilde{\omega}$ is the curvature of $\tilde{\omega}$, then $\mathcal{F}^a = \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a dx^\mu \wedge dx^\nu$ ($0 \leq \mu, \nu \leq D$) would be the total Yang-Mills strength field, including both the spatial and time components with $\mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + f_{bc}^a A_\mu^b A_\nu^c$, where $A_\mu^a dx^\mu \otimes t_a$, the Yang-Mills potential, is the pull-back of $\tilde{\omega}$ through some smooth local section of $G \hookrightarrow \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$. Moreover, set $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega$ to be induced metric on \mathcal{P} form \mathbf{g} and $\tilde{\omega}$. Upon (2.7) and (2.8) we can similarly prove that

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{ab}^\omega = \delta_{ab}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\mu a}^\omega = \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{a\mu}^\omega = \delta_{ab} \alpha_\mu^b, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\mu\nu}^\omega = \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu} + \alpha_\mu^a \alpha_\nu^b \delta_{ab}, \quad (3.11)$$

and;

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\omega ab} = \delta^{ab} + \alpha_\mu^a \alpha_\nu^b \mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\omega \mu a} = \tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\omega a\mu} = -\mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu} \alpha_\nu^a, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\omega \mu\nu} = \mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu}. \quad (3.12)$$

Strictly speaking, we read:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{00} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{0a} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{0i} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{a0} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{ab} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{ai} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{i0} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{ia} & \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\omega}^{ij} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \widetilde{(-g)}^{\alpha\beta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\alpha_0^a & 0 \\ -\alpha_0^a & \alpha_0^a \alpha_0^b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.13)$$

Thus, it can be easily seen that for the Riemann volume form we have: $d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} \wedge d\Omega_G$. Moreover, we read:

$$\langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}, \quad (3.14)$$

and

$$\langle d_0 \omega^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \langle d_0 \omega^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = -\gamma_a^a \gamma_b^a \partial_0 \alpha_i^a \partial_0 \alpha_j^b g^{ij}. \quad (3.15)$$

Consequently, we can rewrite the elements of the Wiener fractal metric (5.33) in terms of the ultimate induced metric $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega$, i.e.;

$$\prod_{i=1}^N \Xi_i = \exp \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \left\{ \langle d_0 \omega^a(t) | d_0 \omega^a(t) \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} + \langle \Omega^a(t) | \Omega^a(t) \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} \right\} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega(t)} \right) \mathfrak{G} \mathfrak{D}\omega, \quad (3.16)$$

and

$$\mathfrak{G} = \prod_{i=1}^N \mathfrak{G}_i = \exp \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} GF(\omega)(t) d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \right) \quad (3.17)$$

Upon the above information we compute:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Omega^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} &= 3f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \partial_0 \alpha_i^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_j^c g^{ij} \\ &= \frac{3}{2} f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \left(\partial_0 \alpha_i^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_j^c + \partial_0 \alpha_j^c \alpha_0^b \alpha_i^a \right) g^{ij} \\ &\equiv -\frac{3}{2} f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \alpha_j^c \alpha_i^a \partial_0 (\alpha_0^b g^{ij}) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

for compact semi-simple Lie group G with totally anti-symmetric structure constant f_{bc}^a . Here, " \equiv " means equal up to total derivative with respect to time. Also, similar to (2.15) we can easily obtain:

$$\mathbf{d}^\dagger \tilde{\omega}^a = -\text{div}(\tilde{\omega}^a) = 0, \quad (3.19)$$

wherein \mathbf{d}^\dagger is the codifferential operator on \mathcal{P} due to the metric $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}$.

All in all, based on **Theorem 1** one obtains;

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{8} \langle \mathcal{F}^a | \mathcal{F}^a \rangle_{\mathbf{g}} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} = \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathbf{d}\tilde{\omega}^a | \mathbf{d}\tilde{\omega}^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + c_0 \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle d\omega^a | d\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle d\omega^a | d_0\omega^a + d\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \\ &+ \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle d_0\omega^a + d\beta^a | d_0\omega^a + d\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + c_0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

Equivalently, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{8} \langle \mathcal{F}^a | \mathcal{F}^a \rangle_{\mathbf{g}} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} = \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{\Omega}^a | \tilde{\Omega}^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} F_{ij}^a F_{kl}^a g^{ik} g^{jl} dx^0 \wedge d\Omega_g - \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \partial_0 \omega_\alpha^a \partial_0 \omega_\beta^a \tilde{g}^{\alpha\beta} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \\ &+ \int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle \nabla\beta^a | \nabla\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \nabla\beta^a | \Omega^a + d_0\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \Omega^a | d_0\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \left\{ \langle d_0\omega^a | d_0\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + \langle \Omega^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \right\} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \nabla\beta^a | \nabla\beta^a + 2(\Omega^a + d_0\omega^a) \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

for

$$\nabla\beta^a = \mathbf{d}\beta^a + f_{bc}^a \tilde{\omega}^b \wedge \beta^c = d\beta^a + f_{bc}^a \omega^b \wedge \beta^c = \left(\partial_\alpha \omega_0^a + f_{bc}^a \omega_\alpha^b \omega_0^c \right) dx^\alpha \wedge dx^0, \quad (3.22)$$

where in the second line of (3.21) we effectively employed (2.8) which establishes the fact that the space-time components of the inverse of the induced metric $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}$ (i.e. $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\mu\nu}$) coincide identically with those of the Lorentzian metric \mathbf{g} (i.e. $\mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu}$) on \mathcal{M} , i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\mu\nu} = \mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu}$ ($\mu, \nu = 0, 1, \dots, D$). However, we easily read:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} = 2\mathcal{F}_{0i}^a \mathcal{F}_{0j}^a \mathbf{g}^{ij} + F_{ij}^a F_{kl}^a \mathbf{g}^{ik} \mathbf{g}^{jl} = -2\mathcal{F}_{0i}^a \mathcal{F}_{0j}^a g^{ij} + F_{ij}^a F_{kl}^a g^{ik} g^{jl}. \quad (3.23)$$

We can also compute the following equalities for the semi-simple Lie group G :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \nabla\beta^a | d_0\omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} &= -3f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^b \gamma_b^c \partial_0 \alpha_i^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_j^c g^{ij} + \delta_{ab} \partial_i \alpha_0^a \partial_0 \alpha_j^b g^{ij} \equiv \delta_{ab} \partial_i \alpha_0^a \partial_0 \alpha_j^b g^{ij}, \\ \langle \nabla\beta^a | \Omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} &= -f_{bc}^a \gamma_b^c \gamma_c^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_i^c g^{ij} \left(\gamma_a^i \partial_j \alpha_0^a + f_{de}^a \gamma_d^e \gamma_e^a \alpha_j^d \alpha_0^e \right) - f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \gamma_a^b \gamma_b^c \gamma_c^d \alpha_0^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_0^c \alpha_0^d, \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

Therefore, upon (3.9) and (3.21) we see;

$$\begin{aligned} dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) &\approx_{\mathbf{I}} \mathfrak{E} \exp \left(\kappa \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} \right) \\ &\times \exp \left(-\frac{\kappa}{2} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \nabla\beta^a + 2d_0\omega^a | \nabla\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{\tilde{\omega}}} \right) \mathfrak{E} \mathfrak{D}\omega, \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

where " $\approx_{\mathbf{I}}$ " means equality up to **Approximation I**.

On the other hand, it can be checked that;

$$\langle \nabla \beta^a | \nabla \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = -f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \gamma_d^d \gamma_e^e \alpha_0^b \alpha_i^c \alpha_0^d \alpha_j^e g^{ij} + 2f_{bc}^a \gamma_a^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \partial_i \alpha^a \alpha_0^b \alpha_j^c g^{ij}. \quad (3.26)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\beta^a | d\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} &= \langle \mathbf{d}\beta^a | \mathbf{d}\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \langle \nabla \beta^a | \nabla \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} + 8f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \omega_0^c \omega_0^e, \\ \langle d\beta^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} &= \langle \mathbf{d}\beta^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \langle \nabla \beta^a | d_0 \omega^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.27)$$

Thus, according to (3.21) we conclude;

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathcal{P}} \frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{\omega}^a | \Delta^{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \tilde{\omega}^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} + \frac{3}{2} f_{bc}^a f_{de}^a \delta^{bd} \int_{\mathcal{P}} \omega_0^c \omega_0^e d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} + \int_{\mathcal{P}} (\partial_0 \omega_0^a)^2 d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} - c_0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.28)$$

The above equality shows that the Yang-Mills action is effectively given in terms of the Laplacian operator (of the induced metric $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega$) just as we have observed in [37, 38] for scalar field theory.

4. LOCALIZING THE WIENER FRACTAL MEASURE VIA SPINORS

Actually, the right hand side of (3.27) resembles the Weitzenbock identity for the Laplacian which describes the Laplacian expectation value of an r -form Λ in terms of the Bochner Laplacian and the Riemann curvature tensor R of the (pseudo-) Riemannian metric q as [32]:

$$\langle \Lambda | \Delta^q \Lambda \rangle_q = \frac{1}{2} \Delta^q \langle \Lambda | \Lambda \rangle_q + \langle \nabla^q \Lambda | \nabla^q \Lambda \rangle_q + \langle \check{\Lambda} | \Lambda \rangle_q, \quad (4.1)$$

with

$$\check{\Lambda}(X_1, \dots, X_r) = \sum_{j=1}^r \text{tr} \left\{ (R(\cdot, X_j) \Lambda)(X_1, \dots, X_{j-1}, \cdot, X_{j+1}, \dots, X_r) \right\}, \quad (4.2)$$

for any collection of tangent vectors $\{X_j\}_{j=1}^r$. Upon Weitzenbock's formula we have the following identity on a closed (pseudo-) Riemannian manifold (Q, q) :

$$\int_Q \langle \Lambda | \Delta^q \Lambda \rangle_q d\Omega_q = \int_Q \langle \nabla^q \Lambda | \nabla^q \Lambda \rangle_q d\Omega_q + \int_Q \langle \check{\Lambda} | \Lambda \rangle_q d\Omega_q, \quad (4.3)$$

wherein the first integral on the right hand side, the so called Bochner term, is effectively equal to the first three terms of the last equality of (??). Let us see more details of $\nabla \beta$. It can be easily checked that according to (3.22) $\nabla \beta$ can be extended to a covariant derivative on $T^* \mathcal{P} \otimes E_{\mathfrak{g}}$, where $E_{\mathfrak{g}} = \mathcal{P} \times \mathfrak{g}$ is the trivial vector bundle of the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} . Indeed, we would approximate ∇ by $\nabla^{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} : \Lambda^1(\mathcal{P}) \otimes C^\infty(E) \rightarrow \Lambda^1(\mathcal{P}) \otimes \Lambda^1(\mathcal{P}) \otimes C^\infty(E)$. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \beta^a &= \nabla^{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} (\omega_0^a dx^0) = dx^\alpha \otimes \partial_\alpha \omega_0^a dx^0 - \tilde{\Gamma}_{\sigma\rho}^0 \omega_0^a dx^\sigma \otimes dx^\rho \\ &= \partial_0 \omega_0^a dx^0 \otimes dx^0 + \partial_i \omega_0^a dx^i \otimes dx^0 + f_{bc}^a \beta^b \gamma_a^c dy^a \otimes dx^0 - \tilde{\Gamma}_{\sigma\rho}^0 \omega_0^a dx^\sigma \otimes dx^\rho \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

since $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\sigma\rho}^0 = \frac{1}{2} \partial_0 \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_{\sigma\rho}^\omega$ and, hence:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Gamma}_{00}^0 &= \tilde{\Gamma}_{0\alpha}^0 = \tilde{\Gamma}_{\alpha 0}^0 = \tilde{\Gamma}_{ab}^0 = 0, & \tilde{\Gamma}_{ia}^0 &= \tilde{\Gamma}_{ai}^0 = -\frac{1}{2} \delta_{ab} (\partial_i \alpha_0^b - \partial_0 \alpha_i^b), \\ \tilde{\Gamma}_{ij}^0 &= \Gamma_{ij}^0 - \frac{1}{2} \delta_{ab} \left\{ \alpha_i^a (\partial_j \alpha_0^b + \partial_0 \alpha_j^b) + \alpha_j^a (\partial_i \alpha_0^b + \partial_0 \alpha_i^b) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

\mathcal{M} as

$$\nabla\beta^a = d_{\mathcal{M}}\beta^a + f_{bc}^a \tilde{\omega}^b \wedge \beta^c, \quad (4.6)$$

while, it is easily seen that if P is a trivial bundle, $P = M \times G$, then;

$$d_{\mathcal{M}}^\dagger \beta^a = -\partial_0 \omega_0^a = -\gamma_a^a \partial_0 \alpha_0^a, \quad (4.7)$$

wherein $d_{\mathcal{M}}$ is the exterior differential operator on $\mathcal{M} = [-T, T] \times M$ and $d_{\mathcal{M}}^\dagger$ is its adjoint with respect to $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega$. Therefore, upon to (3.27) we conclude that;

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \nabla\beta^a | \nabla\beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} + \int_{\mathcal{P}} (\partial_0 \omega_0^a)^2 d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \langle \alpha_0^a | \Delta^{\mathbf{g}} \alpha_0^a \rangle_{\mathbf{g}} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} - 2f_{a,bc} \int_{\mathcal{M}} (\partial_i \alpha_0^a) g^{ij} \alpha_j^b \alpha_0^c d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} - f_{bc,de} \int_{\mathcal{M}} (\alpha_i^b \alpha_j^d g^{ij}) \alpha_0^c \alpha_0^e d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left(\alpha_0^a \left\{ \Delta^{\mathbf{g}} \delta_{ab} + 2f_{ac,b} g^{ij} \alpha_i^c \partial_j + f_{ac,db} \alpha_0^c \alpha_0^d g^{ij} \right\} \alpha_0^b \right) d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

for

$$f_{a,bc} = f_{bc,a} = f_{bc}^a \int_G \gamma_a^a \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c d\Omega_G, \quad f_{bc,de} = f_{bc,de}^a \int_G \gamma_b^b \gamma_c^c \gamma_d^d \gamma_e^e d\Omega_G. \quad (4.9)$$

Actually, since $\int_{\mathcal{P}} (\partial_0 \omega_0^a)^2 d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \int_{\mathcal{M}} (\partial_0 \alpha_0^a)^2 d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}}$, by employing the periodicity condition in the time dimension we would obtain:

$$\int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \beta^a | \nabla^\dagger \nabla \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} = \int_{\mathcal{M}} \langle \alpha_0^a | \Delta^{\mathbf{g}} \alpha_0^a \rangle_{\mathbf{g}} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} + \text{Perturbative Local Terms on } \mathcal{M}. \quad (4.10)$$

We may refer to $\Delta_B = \nabla^\dagger \nabla$ as the Bochner Laplacian. According to (4.9) and (4.10) Δ_B is, in fact, a local partial differential operator on \mathcal{M} . In addition, since \mathbf{g} is a static metric (i.e. $\partial_0 \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu} = 0$), if ω_0^a is a non-dynamical entity (i.e. $\partial_0 \omega_0^a = 0$), then the Laplacian term on the right hand side of (4.8) would be, actually, a local integral formula on the space manifold M ;

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} \langle \alpha_0^a | \Delta^{\mathbf{g}} \alpha_0^a \rangle_{\mathbf{g}} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} = -2T \int_M \langle \alpha_0^a | \Delta^g \alpha_0^a \rangle_g d\Omega_g. \quad (4.11)$$

More precisely, for static ω_0^a the Bochner Laplacian equals the Laplace operator Δ^g at the leading term as a second order elliptic differential operator. Particularly, the Bochner Laplacian is effectively an invertable matrix for non-dynamical ω_0 , whenever the Wiener fractal measure is restricted to a finite set of eigenvalues of the Laplacian.

However, it must be emphasized that the non-dynamicity of ω_0^a is not a necessary condition for the invertibility of $\Delta^{\mathbf{g}}$. Indeed, if ω_0^a varies with time, then by adjusting T (and considering the periodicity in the time dimension) the Laplacian operator $\Delta^{\mathbf{g}}$ would be also invertible over each finite set of its eigenfunctions. In principle, this conclusion holds even for the non-trivial topology of principal bundle $G \hookrightarrow P \rightarrow M$. To localize the Wiener fractal measure (3.25), as far as possible, one should consider this invertibility and utilize some techniques of linear algebra. Let $C'_{\mathcal{N}}$ be the space of smooth functions on M with Fourier-Laplace coefficients restricted to eigenvalues λ of $\Delta^{\mathbf{g}}$ with $\lambda \leq \mathcal{N}$, set $D'_{\mathcal{N}} = \dim C'_{\mathcal{N}}$,

and denote the restriction of Δ_B to C'_N by $\Delta_{B_N} = P_N \Delta_B P_N$, for $P_N : C^\infty(M) \rightarrow C'_N(M)$ the projection map. One reads;

$$\exp\left(\zeta \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \beta^a | \Delta_{B_N} \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}\right) \mathfrak{D}\beta = \frac{C_\zeta}{\left(\det \Delta_{B_N}\right)^{\frac{D_G D_F}{2}}} = \frac{C_\zeta}{\det\left(\Delta_{B_N}^{\frac{D_G D_F}{2}}\right)}, \quad (4.12)$$

wherein $C_\zeta = (\pi/\zeta)^{(D+1)D'_N D_G D_F}$, and $\mathfrak{D}\beta$ is the functional measure of β -forms with the dimension of the form D_F . In fact, we have several options for defining $\mathfrak{D}\beta$. The first choice is to set $\mathfrak{D}\beta \propto \prod_{a,\lambda,i} d\beta_{\lambda,i}^a$, for $\beta_{\lambda,i}^a$ the Fourier-Laplace coefficient of β^a due to $\Delta_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}$, λ the eigenvalue of the Laplacian $\Delta_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}$ restricted to $\lambda \leq N$, and i the corresponding degeneracy index. In this case, we have $D_F = 1$. On the other hand, we may assume β^a to be composed of two independent parameters γ_a^a and α_0^a , each of which has its own corresponding functional measure $\mathfrak{D}\gamma \propto \prod_{a,\lambda,i} \gamma_{a,\lambda,i}^a$ and $\mathfrak{D}\alpha \propto \prod_{a,\lambda,i} \alpha_{0,\lambda,i}^a$. In this case we find $D_F = 2$.

Indeed, the square-root operator appeared in (4.12) is actually given in terms of the square-root of the Laplacian $\Delta^{\mathbf{g}}$ perturbed by some compensating term of lower derivatives which must be given by the associated Ehresmann connection form $\tilde{\omega} = \tilde{\omega}_\mu^a dx^\mu \otimes t_a$. Actually, assuming that M is a spin manifold (hence \mathcal{M} would be too), one may readily employ the Lichnerowicz formula for the Bochner Laplacian on spinor bundle [29] and substitute $\Delta_B^{1/2}$ with the perturbed Dirac operator

$$\Delta_B^{1/2} = \mathcal{D}_\Psi \otimes I_{D_S} = \gamma^{\mathbf{a}} e_{\mathbf{a}}^\mu \left\{ \partial_\mu + \hat{\omega}_\mu + \Psi(A_\nu^a dx^\nu \otimes t_a) \right\} \otimes I_{D_S} \quad (4.13)$$

over the spinor fields on \mathcal{M} , wherein $\{e_{\mathbf{a}} = e_{\mathbf{a}}^\mu \partial_\mu\}_{\mathbf{a}=0}^D$ is a vielbine tangent frame on \mathcal{M} (with $e_0 = \partial_0$), $\{\gamma^{\mathbf{a}}\}_{\mathbf{a}=0}^D$ are the Dirac matrices of the vielbine frame, $\hat{\omega}_i$ is the connection form of the spinor bundle $\mathbb{C}^{D_S} \hookrightarrow S\mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ induced by the Levi-Civita connection of tangent bundle $\mathbb{R}^{D+1} \hookrightarrow T\mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$, $\Psi(A_\mu^a dx^\mu \otimes t_a)$ is a pseudo-differential operator of order < 1 , and I_{D_S} is the identity matrix in $D_S = 2^{[(D+1)/2]}$ dimensions of the spinor space of \mathcal{M} . On the other hand, for Grassmann-valued spinor fields η and $\bar{\eta}$, the Berezin integral formula leads to:

$$\exp\left(\int_{\mathcal{M}} \bar{\eta} \mathcal{D}_\Psi \eta d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}}\right) \mathfrak{D}\eta \mathfrak{D}\bar{\eta} = \det \Delta_B^{\frac{D_\eta}{2}}, \quad (4.14)$$

for $\mathfrak{D}\eta \mathfrak{D}\bar{\eta}$ the Grassmannian measure of the Berezin integral, while D_η is indeed the dimension of the corresponding Grassmannian space, or equivalently the dimension of the fermionic fields due to Grassmannian variables η and $\bar{\eta}$. That is, if one readily replaces the field of Fourier-Dirac coefficients \mathbb{R} with the real anti-commutative Grassmann algebra⁴ \mathbb{R}_S by transferring from \mathbb{R} to $\mathbb{R} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{R}_S$, one would obtain an appropriate compensating local term such as (4.14) for the Wiener fractal measure (3.25). Furthermore, the pseudo-differential operator Ψ could be estimated by Taylor expansion, while by Weitzenböck's formula (4.3) it is obvious that $\Psi(0)$ depends on the curvature of $P \rightarrow M$, hence for trivial topology of P we have; $\Psi(0) = 0$. Therefore, by transferring to the Clifford algebra via $dx^\mu \mapsto e_{\mathbf{a}}^\mu \gamma^{\mathbf{a}}$ for representing dx^μ on the spinor space we may consider the following expansion formula;

$$\Psi(A_\mu^a dx^\mu \otimes t_a) = \Psi(0) + \Psi'(0) A_\mu^a e_{\mathbf{a}}^\mu \gamma^{\mathbf{a}} \otimes t_a + \mathcal{O}(\tilde{\omega}^2) := m_0 + g_0 A_\mu^a e_{\mathbf{a}}^\mu \gamma^{\mathbf{a}} \otimes t_a + \mathcal{O}(\tilde{\omega}^2; \partial_\mu), \quad (4.15)$$

⁴ See [33].

where t_a s are considered in some appropriate representation of the gauge group G , $m_0 := \Psi(0)$ is, in fact, the fermion mass considered for non-trivial topology of P , and $g_0 := \Psi'(0)$ effectively plays the role of coupling constant. Actually, the coupling constant g_0 could be easily absorbed within the structure constant f_{bc}^a in the Yang-Mills Lagrangian density, while the curvature dependent mass m_0 appears as a topological feature. Usually, we set $m_0 = 0$ within the standard model on flat spacetime (before spontaneous symmetry breaking of the vacuum due to the Higgs mechanism), and regard g_0 as the unique coupling constant in theoretical models of grand unified theory (GUT) which aim to unify all elementary particle forces.

In principle, incorporating the Taylor expansion (4.15) into the Wiener fractal measure (3.25) would provide a number of significant similarities between well-known discoveries of particle physics and the theoretical achievements of the Wiener stochastic process for fractal geometric structures on principal bundle P . In order to see this with more details one may need another approximating approach for simplifying the Wiener fractal measure (3.25):

Approximation II: *We should consider the following replacement in the perturbed Dirac operator \mathcal{D}_Ψ ;*

$$\mathcal{D}_\Psi = \gamma^a e_a^\mu \left\{ \partial_\mu + \widehat{\omega}_\mu + \Psi(A_\nu^a dx^\nu \otimes t_a) \right\} \mapsto \mathcal{D}_A = \gamma^a e_a^\mu \left\{ \partial_\mu + m_0 + \widehat{\omega}_\mu + g_0 A_\mu^a t_a \right\}, \quad (4.16)$$

for t_a s being given in some appropriate representation of compact Lie group G .

Therefore, the Wiener fractal measure (3.25) would be;

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) \approx_{\mathbf{I,II}} \bar{\mathcal{C}} \exp \left(\kappa \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^a \mathcal{F}_{\sigma\lambda}^a \mathbf{g}^{\mu\sigma} \mathbf{g}^{\nu\lambda} d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} \right) \times \exp \left(-\kappa \int_{\mathcal{M}} \bar{\eta} \mathcal{D}_A \eta d\Omega_{\mathbf{g}} \right) \bar{\mathfrak{G}} \mathfrak{D}\omega \mathfrak{D}\beta \mathfrak{D}\eta \mathfrak{D}\bar{\eta}, \quad (4.17)$$

for $\bar{\mathcal{C}} = C_\zeta \mathfrak{C}$, and for $\bar{\mathfrak{G}} = \exp(-\kappa \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle d_0 \omega^a | \nabla \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega}) \mathfrak{G}$ the total gauge fixing term, while " $\approx_{\mathbf{I,II}}$ " shows equality via **Approximation I** and **Approximation II**. Obviously, the numbers of the fermionic fields' components (i.e. the components of η or $\bar{\eta}$) must be specified precisely to compensate the resultant determinant of (4.12) due to integration on $\mathfrak{D}\beta$ via (4.14). We address this issue in the following.

Let us reconsider the Bochner Laplacian Δ_B from the viewpoint of the Dirac fermions. Actually, Δ_B in (4.12) acts on the space of one-forms (having $(D+1)D_F$ dimensions) with D_G group indices and hence, consists of D_F copies of Laplacian operator $\Delta^{\mathbf{g}}$ for each space-time dimension $\mu \in \{0, \dots, D\}$ and each group index $a \in \{1, \dots, D_G\}$. Hence;

$$\det \Delta_B \propto (\det \Delta^{\mathbf{g}})^{(D+1)D_G D_F}. \quad (4.18)$$

Therefore, we have:

$$\exp \left(\zeta \int_{\mathcal{P}} \langle \beta^a | \Delta_{B_N} \beta^a \rangle_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^\omega} \right) \mathfrak{D}\beta \propto (\det \Delta^{\mathbf{g}})^{-(D+1)D_G D_F / 2}. \quad (4.19)$$

As mentioned above, the perturbed Dirac action (4.14) has to comprise appropriate numbers of spinor field components given in terms of the (chiral) Dirac fields and the group representation indices, i.e.,

$\eta = \{\eta^a\}$ (resp. $\bar{\eta} = \{\bar{\eta}^a\}$), with;

$$\bar{\eta} \mathcal{D}_A \eta = \bigoplus_{a=1}^{D_G} \bar{\eta}^a \mathcal{D}_A^a \eta^a, \quad \mathcal{D}_A^a = \gamma^a e_a^\mu \left\{ \partial_\mu + m_0 + \hat{\omega}_\mu + e_0 A_\mu^b t_b^{(a)} \right\}, \quad (4.20)$$

wherein the superscript a for \mathcal{D}_A^a (or η^a and $\bar{\eta}^a$) indicates the special representation of the Yang-Mills connection matrices t_b s for the a -th fermion, simply denoted by $t_b^{(a)}$. Thus, according to the Wiener fractal measure (4.17) and equations (4.14), (4.18), and (4.19), the total dimension of fermions D_η must equal the total dimension of $\Delta_{B_{\mathcal{N}}}\beta$, i.e.,

$$D_\eta = (D + 1)D_G D_F. \quad (4.21)$$

The above equation is the most challenging formula for examining the agreement between our method of study in this paper and the substantial structures of the Standard Model, the Georgi-Glashow model of (GUT) [17], and $\mathcal{N} = 2$ Supersymmetric Yang-Mills Theory. It is easily seen that we precisely obtain the Standard Model structure for massive neutrinos ν_e , ν_μ , and ν_τ and complex β^a ; The total Grassmannian components of fermions (with both chirality of neutrinos ν_e , ν_μ , ν_τ) is:

$$D_\eta = 3 (\text{colors}) \times 6 (\text{quarks}) \times 4 (\text{components}) + 6 (\text{leptons}) \times 4 (\text{components}) = 96,$$

while the total gauge group is $G = U(1) \times SU(2) \times SU(3)$ with $D_G = 12$, and the dimension of space-time is $D + 1 = 4$. Therefore, for complex β^a we readily find:

$$(D + 1)D_G D_F = 96.$$

Although this achievement is extremely important and shows that the investigation of Brownian motion of gauge fields in the Hilbert space of the corresponding quantum states may have a profound relationship with the fundamental structures of the Standard Model of elementary particles, it relies on complex gauge fields in the path-integral formulation of the Standard Model,⁵ which does not align with the prevailing approaches. However, this conclusion reinforces the robustness of the Georgi-Glashow model of $SU(5)$ -gauge theory, since it contains exactly the same fermions as the Standard Model. Hence, the Georgi-Glashow model also includes $D_\eta = 96$ Grassmannian components provided the neutrinos ν_e , ν_μ , and ν_τ are massive particles. Thus, for real β^a (i.e. $D_F = 1$), as usually supposed, the equation (4.21) gives rise to $D_G = 24$, which is the case for $SU(5)$ in the GUT.

Nevertheless, the most comprehensive realization for our calculation is $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetric Yang-Mills theory. In this case, we have two Majorana spinors for each group index a and hence, we have:

$$D_\eta = 2 (\mathcal{N} = 2 \text{ supersymmetry}) \times 2 (\text{components of fermions}) \times D_G (\text{group indices}) = 4D_G,$$

which is equal to $(D + 1)D_G$ for any gauge group G and four-dimensional space-time. We have to insist that $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetric Yang-Mills theory satisfies (4.21) only for two- and four-dimensional space-time manifolds, since if $D + 1 = 2n$, then the Majorana spinors will have 2^{n-1} components, and hence: $D_\eta = 2^n D_G$. Thus, to have a well-defined Wiener fractal measure we must have $2^n = 2n$, which

⁵ Because of the underlying Lorentz symmetry the gauge fields' time components cannot be complex while their spatial components are assumed to be real.

is true only for $n = 1$ (two-dimensional space-time) and $n = 2$ (four-dimensional space-time). It must be emphasized that the $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetric Yang-Mills theory is in strong structural agreement with the Wiener fractal measure (4.17) from various points of view because the spinor fields in the mentioned measure are practically partners of the gauge fields. Hence, the existence of supersymmetric invariance (an inherent symmetry that converts boson fields to their fermion counterparts) is naturally expected in (4.17).

5. EINSTEIN-HILBERT ACTION FOR THE STANDARD MODEL ON S^3

Let us revisit the symmetric Wiener measure (5.32) once again. Suppose that we need to perform a linear transformation $F_i : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$ at each intermediate time section t_i , $1 \leq i \leq N$. Then, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) &= \mathfrak{C}_N \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_N)^{D/2}} e^{-|\Delta x'_N|^2/2\tau_N} d^D \Delta x'_N \times \dots \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_1)^{D/2}} e^{-|\Delta x'_1|^2/2\tau_1} d^D \Delta x'_1 \\ &= \mathfrak{C}_N \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_N)^{D/2}} e^{-|F_N(\Delta x_N)|^2/2\tau_N} d^D F_N(\Delta x_N) \times \dots \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_1)^{D/2}} e^{-|F_1(\Delta x_1)|^2/2\tau_1} d^D F_1(\Delta x_1) \quad (5.1) \\ &= \mathfrak{C}_N \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_N)^{D/2}} e^{-|F_N(\Delta x_N)|^2/2\tau_N} J_N d^D \Delta x_N \times \dots \times \frac{1}{(2\pi\tau_1)^{D/2}} e^{-|F_1(\Delta x_1)|^2/2\tau_1} J_1 d^D \Delta x_1, \end{aligned}$$

for $\Delta x_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$, and $\mathfrak{C}_N = \left(\frac{2T}{\tau_{N+1}}\right)^{D/2} \exp(|x'_F - x'_I|^2/4T - |x'_F - x'_N|^2/2\tau_{N+1})$,⁶ where J_i is the Jacobian determinant of transformation F_i , and $\Delta x'_i = F_i(\Delta x_i)$. Here, we have assumed that $\{x'_i\}$ and $\{x_i\}$ are respectively the static and the dynamic coordinate systems on \mathbb{R}^D .

We can simply employ (5.1) for a dynamical geometry of the space manifold M . This geometric evolution is assumed to be absolutely independent of the topology of M , but rather it would have been related to the differential geometric structures, such as the Riemannian metric g .⁷ Therefore, since the Wiener fractal measure was worked out for the Fourier expansion in terms of the Laplacian eigenfunctions on (M, g) , the time evolution of g would cause some change of variables within the measure as we established in (5.1). The next theorem provides a consistent framework for such transformations versus infinitesimal variation of the metric.⁸

Theorem 2 (ref. [2]); *Let $\tilde{g}(t) = \tilde{g} + t\tilde{h}$, $|t| \ll 1$, be a small variation of the metric on the Riemannian manifold (X, \tilde{g}) , for \tilde{h} a symmetric $(0, 2)$ -tensor field on X . Set $\Delta^{\tilde{g}(t)}$ and $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}(t)}$ to be respectively the Laplacian operator and the Riemann volume form due to the metric $\tilde{g}(t)$. Consider the action of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}(t)}$ on $L^2(\Lambda^r(M))$, the Hilbert space of r -forms on X , with the inner product*

$$(u_1|u_2)_t = \int_X u_1 \wedge \star_{\tilde{g}(t)} u_2 = \int_X \langle u_1|u_2 \rangle_{\tilde{g}(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}(t)}.$$

Let λ be an eigenvalue of $\Delta = \Delta^{\tilde{g}(0)}$ with degeneracy space D_λ labeled by i . Then, there exists $u_{\lambda,i}(t) \in \Lambda^r(X)$ for each $\lambda \in \text{spec}\Delta$ and $i \in D_\lambda$ such that;

⁶ The contribution of x_N in \mathfrak{C}_N would provide an integration on the last time section within the total action, hence it is essentially a null set integral and can be easily removed from the calculations.

⁷ To see the corresponding topological dependence see [14–16].

⁸ For the variation of eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the Laplacian (and its generalized versions such as (p, q) -Laplacian and the Witten Laplacian) versus the metric evolution see [1–4, 6, 7, 12, 13, 25, 27, 29] and the references therein

- a) $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^{(t)}} u_{\lambda,i}(t) = \lambda_i(t) u_{\lambda,i}(t)$.
- b) $\lambda_i(t)$ and $u_{\lambda,i}(t)$ depend analytically on t with $\lambda_i(0) = \lambda$ for each $i \in D_\lambda$.
- c) $\{u_{\lambda,i}(t)\}_{\lambda \in \text{spec} \Delta}^{i \in D_\lambda}$ is orthonormal with respect to the inner product $(\cdot | \cdot)_t$.

In the above theorem the manifold X is the total space P of the principal bundle (P, π, M, G) . However, the Wiener's measure (5.1) is, in fact, considered on the base manifold M . As previously mentioned, the Wiener Brownian motion is actually an entropic effect whose origin stems from the second law of thermodynamics. On the other hand, the second law of thermodynamics causes the geometric evolution of the underlying manifold via the Hamilton-Perelman Ricci flow. Therefore, to consider the whole features of the Wiener Brownian motion of the quantum states on M one must incorporate the Ricci flow in the calculations to produce a dynamical background geometry. Actually, we should assume that the space metric would varies with the Ricci flow:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} g_{ij}(t) = -2Ric_{ij}(t), \quad (5.2)$$

for $Ric(t)$ the Ricci curvature of evolving metric $g(t)$ on base manifold M . In fact, as we will argue in the following, we regard the Ricci flow as an imposed natural entropic gauge fixing term for Einstein's field equation. One should note that although the Einstein equation is scale invariant, i.e. is symmetric with respect to transformation $g_{ij} \rightarrow c g_{ij}$ for some $c > 0$, the Ricci flow disobeys this property. Hence, once the scale of time dimension t is fixed⁹ the Ricci flow fixes the scale of g_{ij} and consequently the space volume. Recently, the Ricci flow has attracted a lot of attention in building a well-defined model of (topological) quantum gravity and several research have shown some theoretical evidence for an intimate correlation between gravity and the Ricci flow.¹⁰

Actually, the Ricci flow has been established to be a very fruitful mechanism to improve metrics in Riemannian geometry whenever M is compact. Indeed, it has been shown that in some specific conditions, the Ricci flow converges to a canonical metric [21–23, 26]. For instance, in his seminal work, Hamilton has established that on each closed 3-manifold with positive Ricci curvature the Ricci flow converges to a canonical metric of positive constant sectional curvature [21]. In this sense, the Ricci flow may be regarded as a natural homotopy between a given metric of positive Ricci curvature and a canonical metric of constant sectional curvature. Moreover, Hamilton demonstrated that in this case the Ricci flow could be resolved within a normalized version of which the volume of the manifold is preserved along with the metric evolution. In principle, whenever the Ricci flow holds and admits a unique solution on $(a, b) \subset \mathbb{R}$, it converges to the canonical metric g_c as $t \rightarrow b$, where g_c is necessarily an Einstein metric, i.e. $\lim_{t \rightarrow b} Ric_{ij}(t) = K g_{cij}$, for some constant K .¹¹

Without loss of generality we may assume that the Ricci flow exists on $(-a, a) \subset \mathbb{R}$, for some $a > 0$. Hence, by rescaling $t \mapsto t/n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the domain of the solution changes to $(-na, na)$, whereas on the right hand side of (5.4) one must replace -2 with $-2/n$. In principle, since we are concerned about the stochastic process in $(-T, T)$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$, the integer n must be chosen as large as we need.

⁹ See Eq. (5.4) in below where the time scale ζ is introduced.

¹⁰ See for example [8–11, 14–16, 18, 28, 30, 31, 40].

¹¹ For: $K = \frac{1}{D} \int_M \lim_{t \rightarrow b} R(t) d\Omega_{g_c} / \int_M d\Omega_{g_c}$, where R is the Ricci scalar.

Generally, the Ricci flow could be rescaled as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} g_{ij}(t) = -2\zeta Ric_{ij}(t), \quad (5.3)$$

for some small positive constant ζ . In the following, we will see that as a very tiny amplitude, ζ couples to negligible terms inserted in the Einstein-Hilbert Lagrangian density. More precisely, it is seen that the Ricci flow scaling factor could be compared with the cosmological constant Λ .

Let consider the Hamilton-Perelman Ricci flow on the total space P . Based on (2.7) for any given Ehresmann connection form ω and each local coordinate system, say (x^i, y^a) , we see that:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}_{ab}^\omega(t) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}_{ai}^\omega(t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}_{ia}^\omega(t) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}_{ij}^\omega(t) = -2\zeta Ric_{ij}(t). \quad (5.4)$$

In addition, it can be easily seen that the variation of the Riemannian volume form $d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}$ with respect to t is given in terms of the scalar curvature $R(t)$:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} = -\zeta R(t) d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}. \quad (5.5)$$

We note that although $R(t)$ is actually a function on M , but here we consider it as an element of $C^\infty(P)$ by assuming its value on each fiber of P be equal to that of the corresponding base point.

The equation (5.5) lets us work out the explicit formulation of the Wiener fractal measure (5.1) along with the Ricci flow evolution of the space geometry. Initially, one should note that we have already considered a normalization condition as:

$$\int_P \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda',j}(t) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} = \delta_{\lambda\lambda'} \delta_{ij}. \quad (5.6)$$

Hence, by variation of (5.6) with respect to t , $0 < t \ll 1$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\lambda,ii}(t) &= 1 - \frac{t\zeta}{2} \int_P R(t) \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,i}(t) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} + \frac{t}{2} \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,i}(t) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{g(t)}, \\ \epsilon_{\lambda,ij}(t) + \epsilon_{\lambda,ji}(t) &= -t\zeta \int_P R(t) \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,j}(t) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} + t \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,j}(t) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}, \quad (i \neq j) \end{aligned} \quad (5.7)$$

wherein

$$\epsilon_{\lambda,ij}(t) = \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,i}(0) | u_{\lambda,j}(t) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}. \quad (5.8)$$

Hence, we would readily set;

$$\epsilon_{\lambda,ij}(t) = \delta_{ij} - \frac{t\zeta}{2} \int_P R(t) \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,j}(t) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)} + \frac{t}{2} \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,i}(t) | u_{\lambda,j}(t) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t)}. \quad (5.9)$$

Consequently, along the variation of g the basis of $\mathbf{C}_\mathcal{N}$ moves linearly by the matrix $\epsilon = \oplus_\lambda \epsilon_\lambda$, for each λ with $\mathcal{N} \geq \lambda \in \text{spec}\Delta$, which means that the Fourier-Laplace coefficients $\omega_{\lambda,i}$ s must be transformed via ϵ^{-1} . Therefore, in (5.1) we must consider F_i to be block diagonal in the orthonormal basis of the eigenforms of the Laplacian operator $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_{i-1})}$, say $\{u_{\lambda,i}(0)\}_{\lambda \in \text{spec}\Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}}^{i \in D_\lambda}$, as $F_i = \oplus_\lambda (F_i)_\lambda$, with;

$$(F_i)_{\lambda,mn} = \delta_{mn} + \frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2} \int_P R(t_i) \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,n}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{g(t_i)} - \frac{t}{2} \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,n}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)}, \quad (5.10)$$

for m and n running through the degenerate eigenforms of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_{i-1})}$ with common eigenvalue λ . Indeed, one can simply consider (5.10) as: $F_i = 1 + r_i$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, where we easily gain;

$$\begin{aligned}
J_i &= \det F_i = \exp \left(\text{tr} \left\{ \ln(1 + r_i) \right\} \right) \approx \exp \left(\text{tr} \{ r_i \} \right) \\
&= \exp \left(\sum_{\lambda \in \text{Spec} \Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}} \sum_{m \in D_\lambda} \frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2} \int_P R(t_i) \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} \right) \\
&\times \exp \left(- \sum_{\lambda \in \text{Spec} \Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}} \sum_{m \in D_\lambda} \frac{\tau_i}{2} \int_P \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{5.11}$$

All the above achievements could be simply generalized to \mathfrak{g} -valued differential forms. To accomplish this generalization the pointt-wise contraction $\langle u|v \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ of \mathfrak{g} -valued differential forms $u = u^a \otimes t_a$ and $v = v^a \otimes t_a$ must be replaced by $\langle u^a|v^a \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$, wherein the summation on the group index a is automatically assumed. We also remember that \tilde{g}^ω is a right-invariant metric on the total space P . Hence, the Laplacian eigenforms $u_{\lambda,i}$ s are all equivariant forms. Consequently, the integrands oi the integrals in (5.11) obtain constant values on the fibers of P . This means that $\langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)}$ and $\langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)}$ are actually functions on M and (5.11) is essentially a local formula. Since each fiber is a copy of the gauge group G equipped with the Haar measure we can simply write (5.11) as below:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_i &= \exp \left(\sum_{\lambda \in \text{Spec} \Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}} \sum_{m \in D_\lambda} \frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2} \int_M R(t_i) \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right) \\
&\times \exp \left(- \sum_{\lambda \in \text{Spec} \Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}} \sum_{m \in D_\lambda} \frac{\tau_i}{2} \int_M \langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)} d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right),
\end{aligned} \tag{5.12}$$

where $\langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)}$ and $\langle u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) | u_{\lambda,m}(\tau_i) \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega(t_i)}$ are considered as functions on M with defining their values at $p \in M$ by evaluating them on $\pi^{-1}(p)$, the corresponding fiber of $P \rightarrow M$.

Incorporating the full expression of the Jacobian determinant (5.11) in the Wiener fractal measure (5.1) leads to a highly complicated formulation for Brownian motion of quantum states in $\mathbf{C}_{\mathcal{N}}$. Therefore, we have to consider a number of approximations of the Wiener fractal measure. Before any assumption we prefer to prove a significant lemma.

Lemma 1; *Assume that (P, π, M, G) is a principal G -bundle over the oriented closed Riemannian manifold (M, g) while:*

- 1) $G = U(1) \times SU(2) \times SU(3)$ with Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{u}(1) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(2) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(3)$;
- 2) P is a compact Lie group with Lie algebra \mathfrak{p} ;
- 3) \mathfrak{p} is decomposed as the direct summation of $\mathfrak{p} = \mathfrak{g} \oplus \mathfrak{h}$ so that \mathfrak{h} is a G -stable subspace of \mathfrak{p} , i.e. for each $h \in G$ we have: $Ad_h(\mathfrak{h}) = \mathfrak{h}$;
- 4) $M = P/G$ is a homogeneous space.

Then, there exists some non-trivial equivariant eigenform u_0 of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ so that $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} u_0 = 0$.

Moreover, we may assume two more following conditions:

- 5) For each inclusion map $i : G \hookrightarrow P$ the linear map $i^* : H_{deR}^*(P, \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow H_{deR}^*(G, \mathbb{R})$ is projective.

6) M is simply connected.

Then D_0 has only one element, i.e. there exists a unique normalized equivariant one-form u_0 so that $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} u_0 = 0$.

Proof; Upon the properties (1) to (4) P admits a left-invariant Ehresmann connection under the left action of the Lie group P [19]. In fact, there is an Ehresmann connection on P , say ω_0 , so that $L_h^*(\omega_0) = \omega_0$ for each $h \in P$, wherein $L_h : P \rightarrow P$ is the left multiplication by h , i.e. $L_h(p) = h.p$ for $p \in P$. It is obvious that

$$d\omega_0(U, V) = -\omega_0([U, V]) = [\omega_0(V), \omega_0(U)] \in \mathfrak{su}(2) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(3) \quad (5.13)$$

for left-invariant vector fields U and V on P . Now, let $\mathfrak{s}_0 = \int_G R_h^*(\omega_0)dh$ be a \mathfrak{g} -valued one-form on P . Since dh is the Haar measure on G , then it can be easily seen that $R_k^*(\mathfrak{s}_0) = \mathfrak{s}_0$ for each $k \in G$. Moreover, we easily see that:

$$Ad_k(\mathfrak{s}_0) = Ad_k \left(\int_G R_h^*(\omega_0)dh \right) = \int_G Ad_k(Ad_{h^{-1}}(\omega_0))dh = \int_G Ad_{kh^{-1}}(\omega_0)dh = \int_G R_{hk^{-1}}^*(\omega_0)dh = \mathfrak{s}_0.$$

Thus, \mathfrak{s}_0 is an equivariant one-form on P and takes its values in $\mathfrak{u}(1)$, the center of the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{u}(1) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(2) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(3)$. In addition, \mathfrak{s}_0 is non-trivial, i.e. $\mathfrak{s}_0 \neq 0$, since if $p \in P$ is an arbitrary point and $U = \frac{d}{d\theta}|_{\theta=0} R_{e^{i\theta}}(p)$, then we have: $\mathfrak{s}_0(U) = 1 \in \mathfrak{u}(1)$.

Since \mathfrak{s}_0 belongs to $\Omega^1(P) \otimes \mathfrak{u}(1)$, then $d\mathfrak{s}_0$ takes its values in $\mathfrak{u}(1)$, i.e. for each $U, V \in T_p P$ we find:

$$d\mathfrak{s}_0(U, V) \in \mathfrak{u}(1). \quad (5.14)$$

On the other hand, we compute:

$$d\mathfrak{s}_0(U, V) = \int_G Ad_{h^{-1}}([\omega_0(V), \omega_0(U)])dh \in \mathfrak{su}(2) \oplus \mathfrak{su}(3). \quad (5.15)$$

Hence, upon (5.14) and (5.15) we see that:

$$d\mathfrak{s}_0 = 0. \quad (5.16)$$

Now, let \tilde{g}^{ω_0} be the extension of the Riemannian metric g to P by means of ω_0 as we defined in (2.5). According to (2.16) and (5.16) we also obtain:

$$\Delta^{\tilde{g}^{\omega_0}} \mathfrak{s}_0 = d^\dagger d\mathfrak{s}_0 = 0. \quad (5.17)$$

Actually, since the values of \mathfrak{s}_0 belong to $\mathfrak{u}(1) = \mathbb{R}$, it can be considered as an ordinary harmonic one-form on P . Thus, it defines a non-trivial cohomology class in $H_{deR}^1(P, \mathbb{R})$ denoted by $[\mathfrak{s}_0]$. Since the cohomology groups reveal topological features of manifolds the cohomology classes are independent of the given metric \tilde{g}^{ω_0} . Hence, there exists a closed one-form $u_0 \in [\mathfrak{s}_0]$ so that:

$$\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega} u_0 = 0. \quad (5.18)$$

However, as we specified before from $[R_h^*, \Delta^{g^\omega}] = 0$ one concludes that u_0 is also an equivariant form. In addition, since $u_0 \neq 0$ we can simply assume that u_0 is normalized, i.e.:

$$\int_P u_0 \wedge \star_{\tilde{g}^\omega} u_0 = \int_P \langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 1. \quad (5.19)$$

This proves the first claim of the lemma.

Now, for the rest part of the lemma we have to note that according to the Leray-Hirsch theorem the property **(5)** guarantees that [24]:

$$H_{deR}^1(M, \mathbb{R}) \oplus H_{deR}^1(G, \mathbb{R}) \cong H_{deR}^1(P, \mathbb{R}), \quad (5.20)$$

provided P is connected. On the other hand, upon the Kunneth formula [24] we read $H_{deR}^1(G, \mathbb{R}) = \mathbb{R}$, since $H_{deR}^1(SU(2), \mathbb{R}) = H_{deR}^1(SU(3), \mathbb{R}) = 0$. Thus, if M is simply connected, which ensures that $H_{deR}^1(M, \mathbb{R}) = 0$, we obtain from (5.20): $H_{deR}^1(P, \mathbb{R}) = \mathbb{R}$. Therefore, u_0 is the unique normalized equivariant harmonic one-form on P . This finishes the lemma. **Q.E.D.**

Since we ususally assume the space manifold M to be the three-dimensional sphere S^3 we can simply assume that there is only one element in the kernel of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ for each Riemannian metric g and Ehresmann connection ω . Therefore, we may consider the first approximation as belwo:

Approximation I: *The double summation $\sum_{\lambda \in \text{Spec} \Delta^{g(t_{i-1})}} \sum_{m \in D_\lambda}$ in the exponent of J_i would be replaced by the dominating leading term $\sum_{\lambda=0} \sum_{m \in D_0}$. On the other hand, since we have: $\dim H_{deR}^1(P, \mathbb{R}) = 1$, there is no degeneracy and the only normalized eigenfunction of $\Delta^{\tilde{g}^\omega(t_{i-1})}$ which is considered in (5.11) is u_0 . In fact, upon the normalization condition (5.6) we may simply assume that $\langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} \approx 1/V_i$, wherein V_i is the volume of M for the metric $g(t_i)$; i.e. $V_i = \int_M d\Omega_{g(t_i)}$. Therefore, we readily obtain:*

$$J_i = \exp \left(\frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2V_i} \int_M R(t_i) d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right) \times \exp \left(\frac{\tau_i}{2V_i} \int_M R(t_i) \langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega} d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right). \quad (5.21)$$

However, if $P = G \times S^3$ is a trivial fiber bundle we can assume g to be the left-invariant metric on $S^3 = SU(2)$ and simply consider ω to be equal to $dy^a \otimes t_a$ on any local coordinate system (x^i, y^a) . Hence, we readily obtain $u_0 = d\theta \otimes 1$ wherein θ is the standard parameter of the circle $S^1 = U(1)$ with $\int_{S^1} d\theta = 1$. In this case we find upon (5.4): $\langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega} = 0$. Thus, the next approximation may be reflected by this special case:

Approximation II: *We may assume $\langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{g}^\omega} = 0$ in (5.21). Therefore, we have:¹²*

$$J_i = \exp \left(\frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2V_i} \int_M R(t_i) d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right). \quad (5.22)$$

The third approximation concerns about the volume of the space manifold M . According to (5.5) one can simply compute the derivation of this volume with respect to t as:

$$\frac{dV(t)}{dt} = -\zeta \int_M R(t) d\Omega_{g(t)}. \quad (5.23)$$

¹² It should be noted that if $\langle u_0 | u_0 \rangle_{\tilde{g}^\omega}$ is exactly equal to $1/V_i$ —as occurs in the case of scalar fields [38]—then one finds $\ln J_i \propto \frac{d}{dt} \int_M R(t_i) d\Omega_{g(t_i)}$. Consequently, the contribution of the Jacobian terms in the Wiener fractal measure, given by $\exp \left(\int_{-T}^T \ln J_i dt \right)$, effectively vanishes. This observation demonstrates that, for the emergence of the Einstein-Hilbert action at the leading order of local approximations, the transition from scalar fields to gauge bosons is essential.

In fact, for any $t_i \in [-T, T]$, we compute:

$$V(t_i) = V - \zeta \int_{\mathcal{M}_{t_i}} R(t) dt \wedge d\Omega_{g(t)}, \quad (5.24)$$

wherein $V = V(-T)$ is the *initial volume of the universe* and $\mathcal{M}_{t_i} = [t_i, -T] \times M$ is the *truncated space-time continuum*. Since $\zeta \approx 0$ we could assume that $V(t)$ evolves slightly, provided the integral of the scalar curvature of the space manifold M is not huge. As we see from (5.24) the coefficient $1/V_i$ is itself given by an integration over the truncated space-time continuum \mathcal{M}_{t_i} . Therefore, inserting (5.24) in (5.21) results in a highly non-local formula for the gravity effects. Thus, the next approximation is reasonable:¹³

Approximation III: *We may also assume that the variation of V_i along the Ricci flow is negligible during the period of time in which we are concerned about the Brownian motion of quantum states on M . Hence, we would simply consider $V_i = V$, $1 \leq i \leq N$, and write the Jacobian determinant (5.21) as:*

$$J_i = \exp \left(\frac{\tau_i \zeta}{2V} \int_M R(t_i) d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right). \quad (5.25)$$

In particular, upon approximations **I** and **II** one can easily extract the contribution of the Jacobian determinants J_i s, $1 \leq i \leq N$, within the Wiener fractal measure (5.1) as:

$$\prod_{i=1}^N J_i = \exp \left(\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum \tau_i \int_M R(t_i) d\Omega_{g(t_i)} \right), \quad (5.26)$$

for $\xi = V/\zeta$, which in the limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. $\tau_i = 2T/N \rightarrow 0$) leads to:

$$\prod_{i=1}^N J_i = \exp \left(\frac{1}{2\xi c} \int_{\mathcal{M}} R d\Omega \right), \quad (5.27)$$

wherein $\mathcal{M} = [-T, T] \times M$ is the space-time continuum introduced above, and $d\Omega = c dt \wedge d\Omega_{g(t)}$ is the Riemannian volume form for the Lorentzian metric $\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu = c^2 dt \otimes dt \oplus (-g_{ij}(t) dx^i \otimes dx^j)$ on \mathcal{M} . We should note that according to the rescaled Ricci flow (5.4) the scalar curvature R of g is in essential equal to the scalar curvature \mathcal{R} of \mathbf{g} up to an overall minus sign and some negligible terms of order $\mathcal{O}(\zeta)$. In fact, upon to (5.4) we see:

$$\mathcal{R} = -R + \frac{\zeta}{c^2} \left\{ g^{ij} \frac{\partial Ric_{ij}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial t} \right\} - \frac{\zeta^2}{c^2} Ric_{ij} Ric^{ij} + \frac{\zeta^2}{c^2} R^2 = -R + \mathcal{O}(\zeta). \quad (5.28)$$

Here, we may set our third approximation law:

¹³ Indeed, as we see in the following the space volume V is effectively equivalent to the Newton's gravitation constant G . In principle, the dynamics of the space volume is formulated with a double integral on $M \times M$ within the Einstein-Hilbert action, hence is due to a non-local contribution of the scalar curvature of M . Therefore, the small variation in the volume of the universe V (hence in the gravitational constant G) is the only mandatory choice we have to consider in the first order approximations of the Wiener fractal measure. However, the slight variation of G has already been formulated by means of a local interacting scalar field theory (i.e. dilaton) via the Brans-Dicke theory [5]. See also [39] for more discussions.

Approximation IV: We would simply replace R by $-\mathcal{R}$ in the Jacobian determinant J_i and ignore the remaining terms of order $\mathcal{O}(\zeta)$, i.e.:

$$\prod_{i=1}^N J_i = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\xi c} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \mathcal{R} d\Omega\right). \quad (5.29)$$

In principle, the above three approximations would provide a sufficient set of assumptions to work out the original formulation of general relativity via the Einstein-Hilbert action. Actually, in a local coordinate system on the space-time continuum \mathcal{M} , say (t, x^i) , we would obtain the following formula for the Jacobian term (5.29):

$$\prod_{i=1}^N J_i = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\xi c} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \sqrt{|\det \mathbf{g}|} \mathcal{R} dt \wedge dx^1 \wedge \dots \wedge dx^D\right). \quad (5.30)$$

Hence, the Wiener stochastic process of fractality on Riemannian manifold M along with the Ricci flow automatically involves the Einstein-Hilbert action of general relativity within the approximations **I** to **IV**. In fact, the emergence of general relativity is merely due to the evolution of the cosmos geometry, hence having nothing to do with possible background interactions of the included matter fields. However, one should note that the analytic structure of the spatial metric g_{ij} fulfills Einstein's field equation via the Euler-Lagrange equations. Actually, although $\mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}$ is affected by the energy-momentum tensor of the matter fields via the optimization of the total action, it must obey the Ricci flow as the imposed gauge fixing term that determines the intrinsic evolution of the space-time geometry.

Following the machinery of the previous section, it can be easily seen that the rest parts of the Wiener fractal measure on the dynamical Riemannian manifold (M, g) would be:

$$\exp\left(-\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi^2 \right\} d\Omega\right) \mathfrak{D}\phi. \quad (5.31)$$

wherein the strategy **A** is considered due. One should note that there is an essential difference between (??) and (5.31); In the former, the space-time metric \mathbf{g} is a static tensor, but for the latter it evolves via the Ricci flow. Moreover, in the latter the Feynman measure $\mathfrak{D}\phi$ is given in terms of the Fourier expansion of the Laplacian operator $\Delta^{g(t_i-1)}$ at the i -th time section, while in the former the Feynman measure is static. All in all, the Wiener fractal measure along with the Ricci flow and after the mentioned three approximations and the strategy **A** becomes:

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) \approx \exp\left(-\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\kappa} \sqrt{|\det \mathbf{g}|} \mathcal{R} + \mathcal{L}_{K-G}(\phi) \right\} dx^{D+1}\right) \mathfrak{D}\phi, \quad (5.32)$$

with $\mathcal{L}_{K-G}(\phi) = \frac{\sqrt{|\det \mathbf{g}|}}{2} \left\{ \mathbf{g}^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi^2 \right\}$, the Klein-Gordon Lagrangian density, and $\kappa = \xi c / \hbar$. Hence, we readily obtain Newton's gravitational constant in terms of fractal, geometric and physical parameters in $D = 3$ dimensions: $G = \xi c^4 / 8\pi \hbar$. Therefore, if we use the standard values of G , \hbar and c we compute: $\xi = V / \zeta = 2.1899700 \times 10^{-77}$ (*m.s*), which shows that the initial volume of the universe V (i.e. the cosmos volume at the start point at which the gravitational effects have emerged) has been extremely small. Indeed, the smallness of the cosmos' initial volume V is, in fact, equivalent to a large amount of the Einstein-Hilbert coefficient (i.e. $1/2\kappa = c^4 / 16\pi G$) in the SI units. Thus, the

extremely small amount of the cosmos' initial volume V , as we explain later, could be regarded as the main reason for the hierarchy problem.¹⁴

To work out a well-defined theory from Wiener fractal measure (5.32) we must employ the strategy **B** once again. We readily obtain:

$$dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) \approx \exp \left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\kappa} \sqrt{|\det \mathbf{g}|} \mathcal{R} + \mathcal{L}_{K-G}(\phi) + \sqrt{|\det \mathbf{g}|} \frac{i\varepsilon}{2} \phi^2 \right\} dx^{D+1} \right) \mathfrak{D}\phi, \quad (5.33)$$

for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, one can consider the Wiener fractal process (5.1) for the Lebesgue fractal measure (2.4) through with the Ricci flow as the more fundamental formulation of quantum field theory in dynamical curved spacetime, i.e. in presence of semi-classical gravity. Hence, based on the above results it seems that the basic source of Einstein's theory of gravity stems from the dynamical Wiener fractal measure via the Ricci flow. We refer to this stochastic derivation of gravitational effects as the *Wiener fractal gravity*. As we discussed in the last section, although including non-local terms the Wiener fractal gravity leads to finite predictable expectation values

$$\lim_{\mathcal{N}, N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbf{C}_{\mathcal{N}}} F^{(\mathcal{N})}(t_N, \dots, t_1) \{ \phi(t_{i_1}) \cdots \phi(t_{i_n}) \} dW(t_N, \dots, t_1) \quad (5.34)$$

for $F^{(\mathcal{N})}(t_N, \dots, t_1) = \prod_{k=1}^N \exp \left(\tau_k \int_M V^{(\mathcal{N})}(\phi(t_{k-1})) d\Omega_{g(t_{k-1})} \right)$ with negative (or bounded from above) and renormlizable interaction terms $V^{(\mathcal{N})}(\phi(t_i))$. This ensures the significance of the Wiener fractal gravity as the fundamental and genuine formulation of Feynman's path-integral measure for quantum field theory in the presence of semi-classical gravitational effects. In principle, considering the Wiener process of propagating quantum states on M and the involved entropic features of the second law of thermodynamics via the Hamilton-Perelman Ricci flow will automatically lead us to the Wiener fractal gravity. Through the next two sections, we try to study the theoretical and empirical properties of the Wiener fractal gravity.

6. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

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¹⁴ See [?] and the references therein for interesting discussions about the relation of the hierarchy problem and the Bayesian statistics, which could be related to our achievements in this paper.

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